

**COMPARATIVE DIAGNOSTICS OF THE METHOD OF CLOSURE OF A TOOTH
SUN USING A FRAGMENT OF AN EXTRACTED TOOTH AND RESTORATION OF
TOOTH CELLS UNDER A BLOOD CLOTT IN PATIENTS WITH EXTRACTED
TEETH**

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Abstract. In the article, 25-45 48 primary patients who applied to the Department of Oral Surgery and Department of Dental Implantology and Maxillofacial Surgery of Samarkand State Medical University are divided into 2 groups. The 1st experimental group is compared with the extraction of various teeth ending with "clot" and the 3rd group with the use of osteoplastic materials after the extraction of the tooth fragments and the alveolar bone volume preservation technique using the osteoplastic material.

From 202 to 2023, scientific research aimed at preserving the volume of alveolar bone tissue was carried out in the departments of "Oral surgery and dental implantology" of Samarkand State Medical University. In the study, 41 patients underwent surgery.

Key words: tooth extraction, use of tooth piece, bone atrophy, bone tissue atrophy, tooth socket.

Introduction: Tooth extraction is one of the most common operations in surgical dentistry. Defects formed in the rows of teeth are repaired with the help of orthopedic treatment. After tooth extraction, alveolar bone atrophy is observed, and this process is associated with the breakdown of the alveolar walls of the tooth. Atraumatic tooth extraction is used in modern surgical dentistry in order to reduce bone fragmentation and surrounding soft tissue injuries [8,3,9,12].

Physiological atrophy of the alveolar bone is observed even when the tooth is removed in a simple way [2,5,6,24,27,36]. Alveolar bone atrophy after tooth extraction is 1 mm horizontally and 2 mm vertically after 1 year, on average. In the first months after tooth extraction, the loss is maximal (more than 1mm) and accounts for 55% of horizontal resorption [11, 15].

The vestibular bone plate of the front part of the teeth is mainly composed of Sharpey's fibers and alveoli, so bone resorption is more pronounced on the vestibular side.

Physiological atrophy of the bone plate occurs in the first 50 days and averages 0.4 mm in cases where the clot is completely removed to remove the root of the tooth. Depending on the general condition of the patient, location of the causative tooth, gum biotype, regeneration potential and age, these values may differ.

The purpose of the study.

To justify and improve the method of closing the volume of the tooth cage with the extracted tooth piece in order to prevent bone absorption (resorption) processes.

Learning object.

The dissertation is carried out in accordance with the principles and rules of evidence-based medicine. 48 primary patients aged 25-45 who applied to the Department of Oral Surgery and Dental Implantology and Department of Maxillofacial Surgery of Samarkand State Medical

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University are divided into 2 groups. Experimental group 1 using the technique of preserving alveolar bone volume using extracted tooth fragments and osteoplastic material, group 2 different groups of teeth ending with "blood clot" and group 3 tooth cells after tooth extraction using osteoplastic materials are compared.

During the years 2020-2022, scientific research aimed at preserving the volume of alveolar bone tissue was conducted at the "Oral Surgery and Dental Implantology" departments of Samarkand State Medical University. In the study, 41 patients underwent surgery.

In accordance with the research plan, the patients underwent tooth extraction: in the main and control groups, teeth were extracted in an atraumatic manner and the size of the tooth cells was preserved as much as possible. After tooth extraction in the main group, a piece of tooth was sawn from the ligament area around the root of the tooth, then a 2 mm thick fragment was fixed in the tooth cage, and in the control group, the extracted teeth grew normally. Thus, all cases were divided into two groups - main and control groups [45,50,51,58,67,70].

In preparation for the operation, irreparable premolars and molars of the upper and lower jaws were removed. A total of 57 teeth were removed.

In most cases, teeth affected by chronic periodontitis were extracted, and damage was observed below the marginal gingival area of the tooth crown [16,18,22,24,39,43]. Chronic periodontitis was noted in 15 representatives of the main study group (68.1%), in 13 members of the control group (68.4%). Damage to the dental coating below the marginal gum level was observed in 5 members of the main research group (22.7%), in 3 representatives of the control group (15.8%).

Perforation of the root of the tooth: was detected in two members of the main group (9.1%), none in the control group. Exacerbation of chronic periodontitis was not found in the main group, but in 3 patients (15.8%) of the control group [1,4,7,9,10,14,17,19,21]. According to Pearson's χ^2 criterion, as in the previous cases, there were no statistically significant differences between the indicators of both groups ($p=0.14$), which means that the groups did not differ from each other according to the reasons for tooth extraction. According to the V-Cramer criterion, intergroup communication is weak ($V=0.058$). Table 1 shows the above data.

Table 1. Reasons for tooth extraction

Reason for removal	The main taste group (n=22)		Control group (n=19)		p	V
	Abs., person	Nis., %	Abs., person	Nis., %		
Chronic periodontitis	15	68,1	13	68,4		
Injury	0	0	0	0		
Tooth crack	0	0	0	0		
Periodontitis	0	0	0	0		
Disintegration of the crown from the level of the marginal gum	5	22,7	3	15,8		

Perforation	2	9,1	0	0		
Chronic				15,8	0,14	0,05
exacerbation of periodontitis	0	0	3			
Odontogenic gagmoritis	0	0	0	0		

Note: According to Pearson's χ^2 criterion, the differences are statistically significant when $r \leq 0.05$.

Many patients had their teeth extracted due to decay of the crown and/or roots due to caries, caries complications, and failure of endodontic treatment (Figure 1).

Figure 1. A tooth to be removed due to deepening caries

Periapical destructive changes in the jaw bones are also one of the reasons for tooth extraction, and this pathological process is clearly visible in orthopantomography (Fig. 2).

Figure 2. Destruction of alveolar bone tissue in the root area of teeth 46 and 47

After curettage in the sockets of the extracted teeth of the patients of the main group, they were closed with the extracted tooth fragment.

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The extracted tooth was divided into transverse fragments using the segmental sawing method. A head and a separation disk were used in this process [63,64,66,68,70]. First, the crown part of the tooth was separated from the root area, then another transverse cut was made, retreating 2 mm above the sawed area. The fragment of the extracted tooth, taken from the front of the neck and with a circular connection on its surface, was fixed surgically and mechanically, and the channels of the fragment were treated with a diamond drill [17,28,32,37,49,53,55,60].

In the initial postoperative period, the patient's condition was evaluated and attention was paid to the following criteria: pain in the area of the removed tooth cage, swelling of the face, the condition of the submandibular lymph nodes, changes in the mucosa of the alveolar barrier in the area of the removed tooth cage, the condition of the tooth cage.

Patients of both groups were included in the clinical examination 7 days after the surgical intervention, and no cases such as pain syndrome, body temperature reaction, swelling of soft tissues of the face, complications in the form of separation of sutures, displacement of the root fragment were detected.

Analysis of the results of clinical observation after tooth extraction showed that after 7-10 days, symptoms of inflammation in the main group were less frequent than in the control group [47,48,52,57,59,63,65].

In the study group, the width of the tooth cage before tooth extraction was 7.25±1.25 mm (7 [6.5;8]), after 4 months it was 6.2±0.5 (6.25 [5 ;9;6,75]) was divided, the change in the width of the tooth cage showed an average of 0.92±0.8 mm (0.75 [0, 5;1.5]). In the control group, the width of the tooth cage was 7.3±0.97 mm (7.1 [6.7;8]), after 4 months it was 4.18±2.2 mm (3.87 [2.5;5 .8]), the average cell width change was 3.2±1.2 mm (.25 [2.1 ;4.25]). The statistical significance of the changes in the control group was greater than that of the study group (p=0.023).

Table 2. Results of both groups maxillary and mandibular frontal incisor width before tooth extraction and 4 months later

Tooth cage height, mm		Search group (n=7)	Control group (n=9)	P
Before tooth extraction	M±SD	7,25±1,25	7,3±0,97	0,87
	Me [Q ₁ ;Q ₃]	7 [6,5;8]	7,1 [6,7;8]	
	(Min-Max)	(6-9)	(6,5-8,7)	
4 months after tooth extraction	M±SD	6,32±0,53	4,18±2,2	0,1
	Me [Q ₁ ;Q ₃]	6,25 [5,9;6,75]	3,87 [2,5;5,8]	
	(Min-Max)	(5,8-7)	(2-7)	
p		0,22	0,037*	
The difference, mm	M±SD	0,92±0,8	3,2±1,2	0,023*
	Me [Q ₁ ;Q ₃]	0,75 [0,35;1,5]	3,25 [2,13;4,25]	
	(Min-Max)	(0,2-2,2)	(1,8-4,5)	

Note: Differences are statistically significant when $r \leq 0.05$ according to the Mann-Whitney test.

Figure 3 - Maxillary and mandibular frontal incisor widths of both groups before tooth extraction and 4 months later.

The average height of the tooth cage of the research group was 9.61 ± 1.4 mm (9.6 [8.5;10.75]), 4 months after tooth extraction it was 8.95 ± 1.51 mm (8, 9 [7.65;10.25]). The average length of the tooth cage in the study and control group was 20 ± 4.5 mm (20.6 [17.1;2]), after tooth extraction it was 17.1 ± 0.8 mm (16.8 [14, 20,25,28,34,44]) showed. On average, the reduction of the tooth cage in the study group was 0.66 ± 0.47 mm (0.83 [0.33;1]), in the control group it was 2.9 ± 1.81 mm (2.7 [1.68; 4.1]) and statistically significant changes were observed in the control group ($p=0.35$ according to the Mann-Whitney test).

Comparative research showed that no statistically significant indicators were observed in the study group ($p=0.53$), and no change was observed in the control group before and after tooth extraction ($p=0.35$).

Statistically significant changes in the height of the tooth cage were observed in the test and control groups before tooth extraction ($p=0.003$) and 4 months after tooth extraction ($p=0.007$).

Table 3. Results of maxillary and mandibular frontal incisor height before tooth extraction and 4 months after tooth extraction in both groups

Tooth cage height , mm		Search group (n=7)	Control group (n=9)	P
Before tooth extraction	M±SD	9,61±1,34	20±4,35	0,003*
	Me [Q ₁ ;Q ₃]	9,6 [8,5;10,75]	20,6 [17,1;23]	
	(Min-Max)	(8,1-11)	(14,2-24,7)	
4 months after tooth extraction	M±SD	8,95±1,51	17,1±3,8	0,007*
	Me [Q ₁ ;Q ₃]	8,9 [7,65;10,25]	16,8 [14,3;20]	
	(Min-Max)	(7,5)10,5	(12,9-22)	

p		0,53	0,35	
The difference, mm	M±SD	0,66±0,47	2,9±1,81	0.05*
	Me [Q ₁ ;Q ₃]	0,83 [0,33;1]	2,37 [1,68;4,1]	
	(Min-Max)	(0-1)	(1,37-5,5)	

Note: Differences are statistically significant when $r \leq 0.05$ according to the Mann-Whitney test.

Figure 4 - Maxillary and mandibular frontal incisor heights of both groups before tooth extraction and 4 months later.

Thus, covering the extracted tooth cavity with a piece of tooth gives more results than when the tooth cavity grows under the blood clot. It allows for the placement of direct removable dentures, as well as the placement of a type of intraosseous dental implant that is sized to match the group of teeth being removed.

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